

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT: This article presents productive, modern and innovative methods of teaching English, in order to get learners more interested in learning English in primary classes.

Keywords: mixed technique, interesting games, primary classes, modern and innovative methods, pantomime.

INTRODUCTION After the independence of our country, the interest in teaching foreign languages has increased and many opportunities have been created for young people. As the first President Islam Karimov said, "At present, great importance is attached to the teaching of foreign languages in our country. This, of course, is not in vain. Today, there is no need to underestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our countries, which are striving to take a worthy place in the world community, for our people, who are building their great future in cooperation with our foreign partners." As a logical continuation of these ideas, the Presidential Decree of December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the system of teaching foreign languages" expanded the opportunities for learning foreign languages. In accordance with this decision, all secondary schools should be taught foreign languages, mainly English, from primary school, to increase their interest in teaching foreign languages, to hold various fun games of English lessons from the 1st grade and at the same time, the transition of students to oral, and from the 2nd grade to modern, innovative methods of teaching the alphabet, reading, grammar began. Recently, the number of people who have learned English in any given situation has increased significantly. This is because it becomes difficult in the process of life without knowing English. But language learning also depends on age. In fact, scientists have proven that children learn language faster and easier than adults. The natural ability of children to learn a language, their strong imitation, the large number of children compared to adults, and the ability to quickly memorize the information they have learned are key factors. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is invaluable. The use of technology is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, reading, listening and speaking). For example, to listen and understand, of course, it is impossible to do this process without a computer,

player, CDs. Listening is one of the most important parts of language learning. This requires the student to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, grammatical rules, vocabulary, and meanings at the same time. The use of modern technologies in the educational process is also an important factor for students to be familiar with and use information and communication technologies. One of the most effective ways is to teach and learn a foreign language using modern technology.

For example:

- When using computers, the student can watch and listen to foreign language videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons;
- It is possible to listen and watch radio broadcasts in foreign languages and TV programs;
- use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are more traditional methods;
- CD players are available. The use of these tools will make the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students

Today, interactive teaching methods are gaining popularity in schools. As we all know, this leads to a significant increase in the level of mastery of students, the acquisition of new knowledge with interest and demonstration of their potential. One of the most important requirements for English lessons is to teach students to think independently. Today, English language teachers use the following innovative methods based on the experience of educators in the United States and the United Kingdom

“Creative Problem Solving” To apply this method, the beginning of the story is read and the ending is referred to the judgment of the students;

“Merry Riddles” Teaching riddles to students is important in teaching English, where they learn words they are unfamiliar with and find the answer to a riddle;

“Quick answers” helps to increase the effectiveness of the lesson;

“A chain story” method helps to develop students' oral skills;

“When pictures speak” method is more convenient and helps to teach English, to develop the student's oral speech, it is necessary to use thematic pictures.

As one of the Chinese inventors, Masaru Ibuka, wrote in his famous book, “Late after three” -“... a child's brain can have an infinite amount of information ...”. It should also be noted that children aged 6-7 years do not understand the meaning of information, but memorize it mechanically. That is why it is important not to start teaching grammar to elementary school students who are learning English. Otherwise, the first step in learning a foreign language can be tiring for the child and weaken his or her interest in learning the language.

In short, teaching language to primary school students is not an obligation, but can serve as a foundation for their future knowledge through fun games and the use of innovative methods. Therefore, if the education system also has the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future we, the future teachers, can develop ways to effectively use innovative technologies. we can contribute

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